

Method for Big Data Management in EPC Firms During Engineering Phase

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Abstract

The Building Information Modelling (BIM) industry has long been focused on the development of software, standards, and interoperability that the industry has moved forward greatly in the last five years. This focus often neglects the volume and variety of the data created from both individual BIM models and federated projects. This research was commissioned to deal with the big data generated in an Engineering-Procurement-Construction (EPC) firm based out of Italy. With a focus on creating Power BI Dashboards to replace manual quality checks with automation of data checks, this research was able to create a methodical approach to extracting, formatting and analyzing data by utilizing Big Data Management (BDM) practices with BIM data. This methodology was obtained after an iterative process of creating several Power BI Dashboards and follows an eight-step process: exploration, mapping, extraction, formatting, visualization, automation, testing, and reiteration. The dashboards created for this research include four qualitative checks and an overall quantitative summary of project performance. The first qualitative dashboard checks the model location alignment in the Common Data Environment (CDE) folder structure and the federated model; utilizing the Autodesk Construction Cloud (ACC) platform and the Navisworks federated model. The second qualitative dashboard was created to check singular model elements for alignment with company standards and tagging conventions. The third qualitative dashboard creates

a bridge between the companies' web based CDE and the construction documentation to ensure model items are loaded in both and the quantities are aligned. The final qualitative dashboard also utilized the ACC Data Connector to Power BI and had a fully automated check for Squad Check Reviews, highlighting department performance and missing reviews. The only quantitative dashboard garnered all data from projects into a summary format to help mid-level managers make informed decisions on project progress and have a historical context to help guide future endeavors for the company. The resulting dashboards are now in use and have saved many work hours for the BIM coordinators of the company due to the degree of automation they provide. Although this research worked contrary to typical academic research due to the focus on deliverables, it created a very beneficial workflow. This was because it allowed the author to create a tried and tested methodology for BIM Big Data Management from the iterations of Power BI Dashboard creation. Future research should focus on the ability to automate the extraction of BIM data to be correctly imported into an analytics software without the need to manually format some of the data.

Dissertation:

Link for full text

Presentation video:

<https://youtu.be/lgKGG9Dw3EM>

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